

A Regions

JUSTICE allows for 57 agents, which translate to 57 countries or regions. For computational efficiency we clustered the countries into 12 regions (Figure 6), as it was done in the regional RICE model (Table 1 shows the detailed clustering).

Figure 6: Regions used in the MOMARL formulation

Table 1: JUSTICE Regional Configuration: List of Macro Regions, JUSTICE Regions, and Corresponding Countries

12 Macro Regions	JUSTICE Regions	Countries
Latin America	Argentina	Argentina
	Brazil	Brazil
	Chile	Chile
	Mexico	Mexico
	Rest Central America	Anguilla, Antigua and Barbuda, Aruba, Bahamas, Barbados, Belize, Bermuda, Bonaire, Sint Eustatius and Saba, British Virgin Islands, Cayman Islands, Costa Rica, Cuba, Curaçao, Dominica, Dominican Republic, El Salvador, Grenada, Guatemala, Guadeloupe, Haiti, Honduras, Jamaica, Martinique, Montserrat, Nicaragua, Panama, Puerto Rico, Saint Barthelemy, Saint Kitts and Nevis, Saint Lucia, Saint Martin (French part), Saint Pierre and Miquelon, Saint Vincent and the Grenadines, Sint Maarten (Dutch part), South Georgia and the South Sandwich Islands, Trinidad and Tobago, Turks and Caicos Islands, United States Virgin Islands
	Rest South America	Bolivia, Colombia, Ecuador, Falkland Islands (Malvinas), French Guiana, Guyana, Paraguay, Peru, Suriname, Uruguay, Venezuela

Other High Income	Andorra	Andorra
	Australia	Australia
	Canada	Canada
	Greenland	Greenland
	Hong Kong	Hong Kong
	New Zealand	New Zealand
	Singapore	Singapore
	South Korea	South Korea
	Taiwan	Taiwan
Europe	Austria	Austria
	Belgium	Belgium
	Baltic States	Estonia, Latvia, Lithuania
	Denmark	Denmark
	Spain	Spain
	Finland	Finland
	France	France
	United Kingdom	United Kingdom
	Greece	Greece
	Hungary	Hungary
	Ireland	Ireland
	Italy	Italy
	Liechtenstein	Liechtenstein
	Luxembourg	Luxembourg
	Netherlands	Netherlands
	Norway	Norway
	Poland	Poland
	Portugal	Portugal
	Czechia	Czech Republic
	Germany	Germany
	Slovakia	Slovakia
	Slovenia	Slovenia
	Switzerland	Switzerland
	Sweden	Sweden
Turkey	Turkey	
Eurasia	Bulgaria	Bulgaria
	Croatia	Croatia
	Other European Countries	Åland Islands, Albania, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Cyprus, Faroe Islands, Gibraltar, Guernsey, Iceland, Isle of Man, Jersey, Kosovo, Malta, Monaco, Montenegro, North Macedonia, San Marino, Serbia, Svalbard and Jan Mayen, Vatican City

	Former Soviet Union	Armenia, Azerbaijan, Belarus, Georgia, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Moldova, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan
	Romania	Romania
	Ukraine	Ukraine
China	China	China
Japan	Japan	Japan
Russia	Russia	Russia
MENA Region	Egypt	Egypt
	Gulf Countries	Bahrain, Iran, Iraq, Kuwait, Oman, Qatar, Saudi Arabia, United Arab Emirates, Yemen
	Middle East	Israel, Jordan, Lebanon, Palestine, Syria
	Western Sahara, Tunisia, Morocco	Morocco, Tunisia, Western Sahara
	Algeria, Libya	Algeria, Libya
Africa	Sub-Saharan Africa	Angola, Benin, Botswana, British Indian Ocean Territory, Bouvet Island, Burkina Faso, Burundi, Cameroon, Cape Verde, Central African Republic, Chad, Comoros, Congo, Democratic Republic of the Congo, Côte d'Ivoire, Djibouti, Equatorial Guinea, Eritrea, Eswatini, Ethiopia, French Southern and Antarctic Lands, Gabon, Gambia, Ghana, Guinea, Guinea-Bissau, Kenya, Lesotho, Liberia, Madagascar, Malawi, Mali, Mauritania, Mauritius, Mayotte, Mozambique, Namibia, Niger, Nigeria, Réunion, Rwanda, Saint Helena, São Tomé and Príncipe, Senegal, Seychelles, Sierra Leone, Somalia, South Sudan, Sudan, Tanzania, Togo, Uganda, Zambia, Zimbabwe
	South Africa	South Africa
India	India	India
Other Asia	Indonesia	Indonesia
	Malaysia	Malaysia
	Other Southeast Asia	Brunei Darussalam, Cambodia, Cocos (Keeling) Islands, Lao People's Democratic Republic, Macao, Mongolia, Myanmar, North Korea, Philippines
	Rest South Asia	Afghanistan, Bangladesh, Bhutan, Maldives, Nepal, Pakistan, Sri Lanka
	Thailand	Thailand
	Vietnam	Vietnam
	Rest Pacific Islands	American Samoa, Christmas Island, Cook Islands, Fiji, French Polynesia, Guam, Heard Island and McDonald Islands, Kiribati, Marshall Islands, Micronesia, Nauru, New Caledonia, Niue, Norfolk Island, Northern Mariana Islands, Palau, Papua New Guinea, Pitcairn, Samoa, Solomon Islands, Tokelau, Tonga, Tuvalu, United States Minor Outlying Islands, Vanuatu, Wallis and Futuna
United States	United States of America	United States

B Additional Information on JUSTICE

B.1 Economy Module

The Economy module employs the neoclassical Cobb-Douglas production function, as outlined in the established DICE and RICE integrated assessment models Nordhaus (2018) (see Equation 10). Here, the notation $Y_{t,n}^{GROSS}$ represents the gross economic output, $TFP_{t,n}^*$ represents exogenous Total Factor Productivity, and $L_{t,n}^*$ represents exogenous labor projections from the SSP dataset. The capital, denoted as $K_{t,n}$, is raised to the power of α , and labor to the power of $1 - \alpha$, where α signifies the capital elasticity in the production function. Capital dynamics at each time step are computed by considering the capital from the prior time step, adjusting for annual depreciation rate δ , and incorporating the current time step's investment, $I_{t,n}$, as detailed in Equation 10a.

$$Y_{t,n}^{GROSS} = TFP_{t,n}^* \cdot K_{t,n}^\alpha \cdot L_{t,n}^{1-\alpha} \quad (10)$$

$$K_{t,n} = (1 - \delta) \cdot K_{t-1,n} + I_{t,n} \quad (10a)$$

B.2 Emissions Module

The economy model converts economic output into carbon dioxide emissions, $\varepsilon_{t,n}$, through the use of exogenous carbon intensity, $CI_{t,n}^*$, which reflects the proportion of fossil fuels in energy production (see Equation 11). Emissions from Agriculture, Forestry, and Other Land Uses (AFOLU) are also treated as exogenous, with values for both Carbon Intensity and AFOLU emissions, $AFOLU_{t,n}^*$, sourced from the SSP dataset. The emission control rate, $ECR_{t,n}$, serves as the model's policy lever, determining the rate of mitigation and emissions for each time step.

$$\varepsilon_{t,n} = CI_{t,n}^* \cdot Y_{t,n}^{GROSS} \cdot (1 - ECR_{t,n}) + AFOLU_{t,n}^* \quad (11)$$

B.3 Abatement Cost Module

Regions determine their abatement costs by using the emission control rate, $ECR_{t,n}$, which varies from 0 (no mitigation) to 1 (full mitigation), to mitigate a portion of baseline emissions. These costs are calculated using marginal abatement cost (MAC) curves, which are derived from the Enerdata dataset providing industrial carbon dioxide abatement levels at various carbon prices from 2025 to 2040. Beyond 2040, carbon price projections from the SSP database are used to create additional MAC curves. These MAC curves help calibrate region-specific coefficients, $AC1_{t,n}$ and $AC2_{t,n}$, alongside a correction factor, $\zeta_{t,n}$. Ultimately, the abatement cost correlates with the $ECR_{t,n}$ policy lever to compute the mitigation cost per time step, region, and state of the world, as outlined in Equation 12.

$$\Lambda_{t,n} = \zeta_{t,n} \cdot \varepsilon_{t,n}^* \cdot \left(\frac{AC1_{t,n}}{2} ECR_{t,n}^2 + \frac{AC2_{t,n}}{5} ECR_{t,n}^5 \right) \quad (12)$$

B.4 Climate Module

The JUSTICE framework incorporates the established Finite-amplitude Impulse Response (FAIR) climate module, a simplified model designed to replicate the behavior of more complex Earth System Models featured in the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project Phase 6 (CMIP6) (O'Neill *et al.*, 2016). FAIR employs a set of six equations to efficiently simulate the global mean climate response to 52 greenhouse gases (GHGs) over the period from 1750 to 2100 (Leach *et al.*, 2021). Total CO₂ emissions, encompassing those from fossil fuels, industrial processes modeled by JUSTICE IAM, and emissions from agriculture, forestry, and other land use (AFOLU), are used to estimate GHG concentrations. Other GHG emissions, as well as data on volcanic activity and solar forcing, are treated as exogenous inputs sourced from the Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSP) and Representative Concentration Pathways (RCP) datasets via the Reduced Complexity Model Intercomparison Project (RCMIP).

The FAIR model's structure includes five equations that compose the standard impulse model utilized for GHG metrics in the IPCC's Fifth Assessment Report, plus an additional equation that integrates state-dependent feedback, addressing nonlinearities in the carbon cycle due to atmospheric decay interactions within carbon and methane cycles. This model functions by converting GHG emissions into concentrations, which are subsequently used to calculate effective radiative forcing, culminating in the computation of temperature response by the climate system. The entire process is primarily divided into three components: the gas cycle, radiative forcing, and climate response (See Figure 7).

FAIR's computational efficiency enables robust exploration of climate uncertainty through a constrained and calibrated ensemble, where uncertainty is quantified in terms of Equilibrium Climate Sensitivity (ECS) and Transient Climate Response (TCR). The initial ensemble consisted of 1.5 million members, capturing uncertainties within the carbon cycle, effective radiative forcing, and thermal responses, aligning with IPCC's estimated ECS and TCR ranges and historical climate data, covering ocean heat uptake, global mean surface temperature, aerosol radiative forcing, carbon dioxide levels, and future warming forecasts from the SSP2-RCP4.5 scenario. This full ensemble was narrowed down to a constrained sample of 1,001 members based on each member's alignment with the likelihood of present-day warming. Each member of this constrained ensemble

successfully reproduces historical warming trends, representing distinct potential “states of the world”, (Smith *et al.*, 2023). FAIR computes the global mean temperature increase, GMT_t , at each time step t by integrating regional emissions from the previous time step $t - 1$, according to Equation 13.

$$GMT_t = FAIR \left(\sum_{n \in N} \varepsilon_{t-1,n} \right), \quad \forall t \in T, \forall n \in N \quad (13)$$

Figure 7: Overview of FAIR Climate Model

B.5 Regional Temperature Downscaler

JUSTICE employs the climate downscaler from RICE50+ to determine the regional temperature response across 57 regions. This downscaler utilizes a statistical technique to evaluate temperature data from 244 countries, leveraging information from the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project to link global and local temperature changes via historical data. It integrates global temperature data from all Representative Concentration Pathways (RCPs), which have been implemented by various global climate models for future forecasts. Utilizing this dataset, a linear regression downscaler is calibrated with region-specific coefficients $TC1_{t,n}$ and $TC2_{t,n}$ to estimate the regional temperature in a given region n_j at time step t_i , based on the global mean temperature rise $GMT_{t,n}$ as presented in Equation 14. JUSTICE then distributes the global mean temperature rise to all regions in set N to derive $GMT_{t,n}$, as outlined in Equation 14a.

$$RMT_{t,n} = TC1_{t,n} + TC2_{t,n} \cdot GMT_{t,n} \quad (14)$$

$$\text{where } gmt_{t,n} = gmt_t, \quad \forall n \quad (14a)$$

B.6 Climate Damage Module

JUSTICE uses the RICE50+ model’s methodology to estimate the damage fraction, $\omega_{t,n}$, which quantifies the portion of economic output lost to climate damages (see Equation 15). This fraction is derived from the impact factor, $\psi_{t,n}$, calculated using the impact from the previous time step, $t - 1$, and the damage function specification, $\sigma_{t,n}$, through a simplified impact formulation (Equation 15a). The damage specification follows Kalkuhl and Wenz’s approach (Kalkuhl and Wenz, 2020), analyzing data from over 1,500 regions in 77 countries. This method utilizes subnational GDP data (Gross Regional Product, GRP) to empirically estimate historical climate impacts over various timeframes and regions. It captures linear impacts on production based on lagged temperature, RMT_{t-1} , and accounts for weather changes by including an interaction term: the product of the annual regional temperature change, ΔRMT_t , and the lagged temperature, RMT_{t-1} . The annual temperature-dependent impact on productivity is calculated using coefficients $DC1_t$ and $DC2_t$, which are applied to both the lagged temperature and the interaction term (Equation 15b).

$$\omega_{t,n} = 1 - \frac{1}{1 + \psi_{t,n}} \quad (15)$$

$$\psi_{t,n} = \frac{1 + \psi_{t-1,n}}{1 + \sigma_{t-1,n}} - 1 \quad (15a)$$

$$\sigma_{t,n} = DC1_{t,n} \cdot \Delta RMT_{t,n} + DC2_{t,n} \cdot RMT_{t-1,n} \cdot \Delta RMT_{t,n} \quad (15b)$$

$$\text{where } dc1_{t,n} = dc1 \quad \forall t, n \quad (15c)$$

$$\text{and } dc2_{t,n} = dc2 \quad \forall t, n \quad (15d)$$

$$\Delta RMT_{t,n} = RMT_{t,n} - RMT_{t-1,n} \quad (15e)$$

B.7 Consumption Calculation

Consumption, represented as $C_{t,n}$, for a region at a given time step and state, is calculated based on its net economic output, $Y_{t,n}^{NET}$, and investment, $I_{t,n}$, as described in Equation 16. To determine consumption per capita, the consumption hypermatrix is divided by the population or labor $L_{t,n}^*$ from the SSP database (Equation 16a). Net economic output is derived by deducting climate impact costs, $\Omega_{t,n}$, and abatement costs, Λ_{TNS} , from the gross economic output, which accounts for the costs of mitigating CO₂ emissions (Equation 16b). The damage cost is computed by multiplying the gross economic output, $Y_{t,n}^{GROSS}$, by the damage fraction (Equation 16c). Investment $I_{t,n}$ signifies the portion of $Y_{t,n}^{GROSS}$ that is saved and reinvested to drive economic growth. This saving depends on the savings rate $S_{t,n}$, unique to each region per time step, which is multiplied by the net economic output to determine investment (Equation 16d). In this study, the savings rate is exogenous, sourced from regional historical data, and aligns with long-term projections from DICE-2016R2 (Nordhaus, 2018).

$$C_{t,n} = Y_{t,n}^{NET} - I_{t,n} \quad (16)$$

$$CPC_{t,n} = \frac{C_{t,n}}{L_{t,n}^*} \quad (16a)$$

$$Y_{t,n}^{NET} = Y_{t,n}^{GROSS} - \Omega_{t,n} - \Lambda_{t,n} \quad (16b)$$

$$\Omega_{t,n} = Y_{t,n}^{GROSS} \cdot \omega_{t,n} \quad (16c)$$

$$I_{t,n} = S_{t,n} \cdot Y_{t,n}^{NET} \quad (16d)$$

C MOMAPPO Setup

We train our agents using MOMAPPO (Felten *et al.*, 2024b), an extension of Multi-Agent PPO (MAPPO) (Yu *et al.*, 2022) designed for multi-objective settings. MOMAPPO generates a solution set of multi-agent policies for cooperative problems by leveraging a decomposition approach (Felten *et al.*, 2024a). This technique breaks the multi-objective problem into a collection of single-objective problems, which are then solved using a multi-agent reinforcement learning algorithm. A scalarisation function, parameterised by weight vectors, is employed to perform the decomposition and focus on different regions of the objective space. In our work, we use the weighted sum scalarisation function due to its simplicity. To ensure consistency across objectives, the environment rewards are first normalised to account for differences in scale. Weight vectors are generated by sampling 100 weights uniformly. For each sampled weight, MOMAPPO trains a multi-agent policy to optimise a specific trade-off using MAPPO. After training, the policy is evaluated on the original environment to estimate its value vector \mathbf{v}^π . If the policy is non-dominated, it is added to the solution set. The algorithm concludes by returning all non-dominated multi-agent policies, providing a diverse set of solutions for various trade-offs in the objective space.

We train MOMAPPO for 1 million global steps, evaluating the performance every (approximately) 20,000 steps. The policies are implemented as Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP) networks consisting of two layers, each with 64 hidden dimensions, and using Rectified Linear Unit (ReLU) activation functions. The training and evaluation is conducted across ten random seeds.